

Microstructure Controlled Fracture Toughness

of SiC/Al Metal Matrix Composites

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Summary

The effects of notch acuity, heat treatment, and orientation on the fracture toughness of SiC/6061 aluminum metal matrix composites have been studied and the results discussed in terms of a microstructure controlled void growth and coalescence mechanism for fracture. The major findings are that the critical crack tip opening displacement is a linear function of the crack root radius and the apparent fracture toughness fits the relation $K_{IC}(\rho) = K_{IC} (1 + \rho/2c)^{3/2}/(1 + \rho/c)$. The fracture toughness also depends inversely on the projected area of SiC in the plane of fracture and this leads to an orientation dependence of fracture toughness controlled by size, shape, and distribution of SiC in the composite. The micro-mechanism of fracture is void coalescence and the behavior is consistent with void coalescence models.

Introduction

Discontinuous silicon carbide/aluminum alloy (SiC/Al) metal matrix composites (MMC's) have exhibited improved physical and mechanical properties when compared to the wrought properties of the matrix alloy. These improved properties include high specific modulus, high creep strength, high fatigue resistance, low thermal expansion and good thermal stability. Both whisker and particulate composites (SiC_w/Al and SiC_p/Al) can be formed using standard metallurgical processing and hence are inexpensive to produce compared to other MMC systems. The tensile ductility and fracture properties of the composite reported to date, however, are inferior to wrought alloy properties. The tensile ductility has been improved by control of process parameters, but relatively little improvement in fracture toughness or notch sensitivity has been achieved. A compilation of K_{IC} data from the literature appears in Fig. 1. Values of K_{IC} for the SiC_w/Al material appear to be independent of the tensile ductility of the material. For the SiC_p/Al material, K_{IC} is observed to increase linearly by a factor of ~1.6 for an increase of tensile ductility from ~0.8% to 4%. This trend for the SiC_p/Al composites was also observed by Harrigan (1).

Figure 1: A Compilation of K_{IC} Data for SiC/6061 Aluminum Metal Matrix Composite

A complicating factor in assessing fracture properties is that methods to measure the toughness in the SiC/Al MMC's have not been standardized. This situation is due in part to the difficulty in fatigue precracking the toughness specimens, especially when the specimen thickness exceeds ~6mm. Fatigue precracking is difficult because the crack initiation toughness relative to the crack propagation toughness is much higher in the composite than in the wrought material. Once the crack initiates, rapid extension occurs at low stress intensity levels.

Although the materials show limited ductility on a macroscopic scale, SEM fractography indicates that fracture occurs by a ductile mechanism with

plastic deformation localized at the crack tip. This produces a fracture surface consisting of fine dimples which are typical of both tensile and fatigue failures (2). The size of the dimples ($\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$) is on the order of the subgrain size of the Al matrix as viewed in the TEM (3).

The above observations suggest that a critical strain criteria at the crack tip may control fracture. Furthermore, the small-scale yielding observed suggests that fracture toughness is linked to the microstructure and the properties of the matrix. Illuminating these controlling factors with the view toward fracture toughness improvement by thermal treatment and microstructural control is the object of the present study.

Experimental

Materials

The materials used in this study were 20V/o SiC_w/6061 aluminum extruded tube, 20V/o SiC_w/6061 aluminum plate, and 25V/o SiC_p/6061 aluminum plate. The whisker composite was obtained from ARCO Metals, Silag Operations, Greer, SC, and the particulate composite from DWA Specialities, Inc., Chatsworth, CA. The SiC in the whisker composites is a mixture of approximately 80% fine whiskers and 20% particulate material. The whiskers are faulted β -silicon carbide with original lengths of up to 50 μm and diameters ranging from 0.2 to 1.0 μm . The particulate SiC consists of irregularly shaped particles with a high percentage having flake like geometry. The SiC is blended with -325 mesh, commercially available, inert gas atomized 6061 aluminum powders. Both whisker and particulate composite billets are formed by cold compaction followed by hot pressing at temperatures above the solidus of the matrix alloy.

The extruded tube material was taken from a 2 cm thick, 32 cm diameter, back extruded cylinder formed from an "as-pressed" billet. The DWA plate material was warm rolled to 6.35 mm thickness. The ARCO plate material was first extruded to form a 12.5 mm x 12.6 cm flat extrusion and then cross rolled in steps at elevated temperature to form a 6.35 mm thick plate. This processing fractured the whiskers and produced a high proportion of whiskers with L/D ratios between 2:1 and 5:1 in the ARCO composite. Microstructures of the materials are shown in Fig. 2. Figure 2a shows the morphology of the whisker and the porosity observed in the plate. The tube material had the same microstructure as that shown in Fig. 2a except that pores occurred with higher frequency in the plate material than in the extruded tube, indicating that these may have been introduced during hot rolling. The particulate material was pore free (Fig. 2b).

Heat Treatments

Plates were tested in a nominal T6 temper "as received" condition. The "as received" condition of the tube was slightly overaged from the T6 condition. Specimens were cut from the tube and heat treated as described in Table 1 to provide material in "as received," T6, degassed, and degassed +T6 conditions.

Mechanical Tests

Rockwell hardness, tensile, Charpy V-notch (CVN), and fracture toughness tests were conducted. Due to the scarcity of material and size limitations, only those orientation variants shown in Fig. 3 were selected.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Microstructure of a) Whisker SiC/6061 Al MMC and b) particulate SiC/6061 Al

TABLE 1: DESCRIPTION OF THERMAL TREATMENTS TO EXTRUDED TUBE MATERIAL

<u>CONDITION</u>	<u>THERMAL TREATMENT</u>
AS RECEIVED	NONE PRIOR TO TESTING.
T6	SOLUTIONIZED AT 527°C FOR 1 HOUR; COLD WATER QUENCHED; THEN PRECIPITATION HARDENED AT 177°C FOR 8 HOURS FOLLOWED BY AIR COOL.
DEGASSED	HEATED TO 500°C FOR 48 HOURS IN A 25 MILLITORR VACUUM. SPECIMEN ALLOWED TO COOL IN VACUUM.
DEGASSED + T6	DEGAS THERMAL TREATMENT WAS USED, THEN T6 THERMAL TREATMENT WAS APPLIED

Figure 3: Orientations of Specimens from a) plate and b) tube

Tensile Tests. Tensile tests were conducted on duplicate subsized specimens in accordance with ASTM procedures. Additionally, two standard 12.8 mm diameter tensile specimens were tested in the longitudinal orientation of the tube to determine any specimen size effect in the tensile data.

Impact Tests. Charpy V-notch (CVN) specimens were prepared from the tube. Triplicate specimens were tested at room temperature in an instrumented Charpy tester in the L-C orientation.

Toughness Tests. The fracture toughness test specimens taken from the plate material had the geometry of a 1/2 T compact tension specimen as described in ASTM E399 except that the thickness was 6.35 mm rather than 12.70 mm. Various notch root radii were produced either by first drilling a hole at the required crack length and then back cutting to the hole or by machining with a tool sharpened to the desired radius. None of the plate specimens were fatigue precracked prior to testing, but several specimens were tested with "pop-in" notches. An MTS displacement clip gage was attached to specimens using razor edges bonded to the specimens with epoxy. Testing was performed in an MTS hydraulic test machine under displacement control at a loading rate of ~ 0.2 MPa/m/sec.

Fracture toughness test specimens from the tube were of standard 1/2 T compact tension configuration. Tests were performed in duplicate. The testing procedure and data analysis conformed to ASTM E399 procedures where appropriate. Data from the study on the effect of notch acuity was utilized to select a valid notch root radius for some of the tests. The study showed a valid K_{IC} is obtained with a notch root radius of less than 80 μm . The notch radius for many of the specimens reported herein was 74 μm . Fatigue precracking of specimens, though difficult, was performed on a number of specimens. Several specimens were precracked in the MTS universal testing machine under stroke control according to the schedule given in Table 2. Other specimens were precracked at the David Taylor Naval Ship Research and Development Center, Annapolis, Maryland (Mr. M. Vassilaros) using a high

TABLE 2: FATIGUE PRECRACK SCHEDULE

STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR K_{MAX} ($MPa\sqrt{m}$)	ΔK ($MPa\sqrt{m}$)	CYCLE COUNT ($\times 10^3$)	CRACK EXTENSION (mm)
3.4	3.2	2070	0.00
3.8	3.7	2180	0.51
5.7	5.6	2300	3.30
5.3	5.3	1650	0.07
5.4	5.1	1800	0.41
5.3	5.2	1830	0.81

stiffness fatigue machine under compliance feedback control. Fatigue precracking produced crack root radii of 2 to 4 μm .

Fractography

Stereo-pair, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) along with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDAX) fractography was performed on representative fracture surfaces. Dimple height, h , measurements were made from the stereo pairs using the relation

$$h = \frac{P}{2M} \left[\sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \right]^{-1} \quad (1)$$

where P is the parallax, M is the magnification, and α is the tilt angle between the stereo pairs. Parallax is measured as the difference in distance between the base of the dimple and the cusp projected on one photograph and that same distance projected on the other photograph of the stereo pair.

Results and Discussion

Hardness and Tensile Strength Properties

The hardness and tensile strength properties for the various materials, orientations, and heat treatments are given in Table 3. Also included in Table 3 are reference values (4) for wrought Al 6061 in the T6 condition.

TABLE 3: HARDNESS AND TENSILE PROPERTIES

	MATERIAL	E(GPa)	σ_y (MPa)	σ_{UTS} (MPa)	% ELONG	R _B
PLATE	20v/o SiC _w /6061-T6 (L)	122	443	584	1.8	84.0
	20v/o SiC _w /6061-T6 (T)	91	409	480	3.8	88.5
	25v/o SiC _p /6061-T6 (L)	99	345	410	4.4	80.5
	25v/o SiC _p /6061-T6 (T)	98	350	409	4.0	82.0
	6061-T6 Al*	69	276	310	17	--
TUBE	20v/o SiC _w /6061-T6 (L)					
	AS RECEIVED	108	335	490	3.4	64.5
		108 ⁺	332 ⁺	463 ⁺	3.4 ⁺	--
	T6	103	375	518	3.0	85.0
	DEGASSED	106	175	365	5.0	56.7
	DEGASSED + T6	108	374	521	2.7	88.6

LEGEND: E = YOUNG'S MODULES; σ_y = 0.2% FLOW STRESS; σ_{UTS} = ULTIMATE TENSILE STRENGTH; % ELONG = THE PLASTIC STRAIN (ϵ_p) AT FAILURE; AND R_B = ROCKWELL B HARDNESS SCALE

* DATA FROM ASM METALS HANDBOOK
⁺ 12.8 mm DIAMETER; ALL OTHER 4.1 mm DIAMETER

Comparison of Al 6061-T6 and SiC_w/Al 6061-T6 properties shows significant increases in modulus, yield strength and ultimate tensile strength due to the addition of the SiC. Whisker additions are seen to be somewhat more effective in strengthening than are particulate additions. Ductility, however, is less and orientation effects are more pronounced in the SiC_w/Al 6061-T6 materials.

The extruded tube ("as received") was to be delivered in a T6 condition. The slightly lower values of yield strength and Rockwell-B hardness (RB) for the extruded tube can be attributed to overaging caused by a low cooling rate from the aging temperature. If the "as received" condition had not had a slight degree of overage, then the yield strength and hardness would be somewhat higher than observed. Tensile specimens of larger diameter were tested from the "as received" material to determine the effect of material sample volume. The results were nearly identical to the subsized tensile data.

The long duration, low temperature solution annealing effect of degassing the tube material reduced its yield and ultimate tensile strengths by 53 percent with an incremental improvement in ductility of ~2 percent elongation. Precipitation heat treating the degassed material to a T6 condition (degassed + T6) restored the yield and ultimate tensile strength to the T6 level, as shown in Table 3. This indicates that little magnesium was lost in the degassing heat treatment. Vacuum degassing at higher temperatures or for longer times could result in the loss of magnesium and the subsequent diminution of the capacity for strengthening through precipitation hardening.

It should be noted that the T6 and the degassed + T6 thermal treatments in Table 1 are the standard thermal treatments for wrought Al 6061 alloys. The effect of the presence of the SiC whiskers on the solution treatment and aging processes has not been extensively studied to date. Harrigan et.al. (5) have presented results for a 30 V/o SiC₀/Al 6061 alloy which indicated that solution treatments similar to those used for wrought Al 6061 are satisfactory while aging response is accelerated. Similar accelerated aging behavior is described by Papazian (6) for whisker material.

Impact Behavior

The effect of thermal treatment on the impact behavior of SiC_w/Al 6061 composite tube material is given in Table 4. Specimen orientation was L-C. The CVN energy values are nearly the same for all the thermal treatments studied. The values are at least an order of magnitude lower than the CVN values of the wrought Al 6061 alloy in the T6 condition. Solution anneal degassing the composite material gave the highest absorbed energy value (1.61 J) compared to the other thermal treatments (0.5 J). Also about 10 percent shear fracture was observed in the degassed specimens compared to no shear in the others. The instrumented Charpy data, shown in Fig. 4, further illustrate the impact energy value differences. The load-time trace for the degassed material exhibits general yielding, while the trace for the degassed + T6 material shows classic brittle behavior.

Dynamic stress intensity values, K_{ID} , derived from the CVN tests are also listed in Table 4 with the corresponding K_{IC} data. Similar results were reported by Strife and Prewo (7). It is interesting to note that the impact energy decreases with increasing yield stress whereas the K_{ID} and K_{IC} fracture toughness increase with increasing yield stress.

Fracture Toughness

Effect of Heat Treatment on Toughness. The effect of heat treatment on the K_{IC} fracture toughness is listed in Table 4. In general, the toughness increases with increasing yield stress, although the trend is not strong. A valid K_{IC} value for the degassed material could not be determined because the ratio of P_{max} to P_0 significantly exceeded 1.10. This behavior requires an elastic-plastic test method such as the J-integral to determine the crack initiation energy. The value of 18.9 MPa \sqrt{m} for the degassed material in Table 4 was calculated using P_{max} and thus is conservative. The levels of all K_{IC} values for the composite are less than 65 percent of the K_{IC} value derived from J tests by Kambour and Miller (8) for wrought Al 6061 alloy in the T6 condition. It is noted that the K_{IC} value for Al 6061 calculated from Kambour and Miller's results is within the range of values of 30.77 to 38.47 MPa \sqrt{m} reported by Kaufman (9). The addition of the SiC whiskers, therefore, is not completely detrimental to the fracture toughness of the Al 6061 alloy.

Effect of Orientation on Toughness. The very strong effect of orientation on the K_{IC} fracture toughness of degassed + T6 composite material can be seen in Table 5. The orientation of highest toughness is L-C, in agreement with the trend found by Crowe and Gray (10). It is speculated that the higher toughness in the L-C orientation results from the reduced amount of projected area of SiC whiskers in the crack plane (i.e., the mean free path between reinforcements is greater).

Effect of Notch Acuity on Toughness. Figure 5 shows the effect of notch acuity on the fracture toughness of SiC/Al. The effect of notch

TABLE 4: EFFECT OF THERMAL TREATMENT ON THE IMPACT AND TOUGHNESS BEHAVIOR OF SiC_w/Al 6061 COMPOSITE MATERIAL (SPECIMEN ORIENTATION L-C)

THERMAL TREATMENT	CVN ENERGY (J)	FRACTURE TOUGHNESS	
		K _{ID} (MPa√m)	K _{IC} (MPa√m)
AS RECEIVED	0.5	19.4	19.5
T6	0.6	20.4	23.4
DEGASSED	1.6	17.5*	18.9*
DEGASSED + T6	0.6	21.8	22.4
Al 6061-T6	23.1**	--	36.8***

* K_Q VALUE BASED ON MAXIMUM LOAD.

** TESTED STANDARD CVN TESTER.

*** CALCULATED FROM G_{IC}

Figure 4 - Instrumented Charpy V-Notch Oscilloscope Traces

TABLE 5: EFFECT OF ORIENTATION ON TOUGHNESS BEHAVIOR

	MATERIAL	K_{IC} (MPa \sqrt{m})
PLATE	20v/o SiC _w /6061-T6 (L)	7.1 (L-T)
	20v/o SiC _w /6061-T6 (T)	6.3 (T-L)
	25v/o SiC _p /6061-T6 (L)	15.8 (L-T)
	25v/o SiC _p /6061-T6 (T)	14.5 (T-L)
	6061-T6 Al*	~37
TUBE	20v/o SiC _w /6061-T6	22.4 (L-C)
		14.0 (R-L)
		17.6 (C-L)

* DATA FROM ASM METALS HANDBOOK

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5 - Effect of Notch Acuity on Fracture Toughness of SiC/6061 Al MMC: a) whisker reinforced plate, b) particulate reinforced plate, and c) whisker reinforced tube.

acuity on the apparent plane strain fracture toughness has been studied by a number of authors (11-13). The trend has been to fit the apparent plane strain fracture toughness, $K_{IC}(\rho)$, data to a discontinuous function of the form:

$$K_{IC}(\rho) = A\sqrt{\rho} \quad \text{for } \rho > \rho_0 \quad (2a)$$

$$K_{IC}(\rho) = K_{IC} \quad \text{for } \rho < \rho_0 \quad (2b)$$

where ρ is the notch root radius, and A and ρ_0 are constants. The power function portion of the relationship passes through the origin. A close examination of the available data reveals, however, that the data usually exhibit a smooth transition between the regions defined by eqs. (2a) and (2b) rather than a discontinuity. Furthermore, a least squares fit to the data often demonstrates a positive intercept. This positive intercept has been interpreted as being related to interactions between the crack and the microstructure (11).

The preceding method in conjunction with crack opening displacement measurements has been used to study the effect of notch acuity on the plane strain fracture toughness of 6.26 mm thick SiC/Al MMC plate (10). SiC/Al composite produced using particulate SiC as the reinforcement exhibited a significant intercept magnitude when a least squares fit was performed, whereas the intercept was close to zero for whisker reinforced material.

An alternate analysis (14) of the data can be performed using the function:

$$K_{IC}(\rho) = K_{IC} \frac{(1 + \rho/2c)^{3/2}}{(1 + \rho/c)} \quad (3)$$

derived to analyze crack tip blunting mechanisms in polymers (15). In eq. (3), c is a characteristic length in front of the crack tip and $c < \rho_0$.

Equation (3) passes through a minimum at $\rho=c$ and for $\rho \gg c$ approximates

$$\frac{K_{IC}}{2} \left(\frac{\rho}{2c}\right)^{1/2}, \quad (4)$$

which has the form of eq. (2a).

Although the fracture criteria used to derive eq. (3) is based on a critical stress, the functional relationship is more useful than eqs. (2a) and (2b). This is because eq.(3) is a two parameter continuous function. The two parameters can be extracted by testing two specimens of finite root radii and the results used to extract K_{IC} from non-precracked tests. The two parameter fit is shown in Figs. 5a through c. The results in Fig. 5c have been used to select the root radius for tests on the extruded tube material.

Agreement with eq. (3) fails at high ρ since the crack does not always initiate normal to the load. In the present study, this deviation from linearity has been observed for $\rho > 800 \mu\text{m}$.

Figures 6 a and b show the crack tip opening displacement at fracture initiation, δ_i , plotted as a function of root radius for the plate materials. This linear behavior implies that the fracture initiation process is strain controlled (16).

(a)

(b)

Figure 6 - Effect of notch root radius on crack tip opening at fracture initiation: a) whisker reinforced plate and b) particulate reinforced plate.

Scanning Electron Fractography

Observations of the fracture paths of cracked, but not separated compact tension specimens were made in the SEM. The crack path was revealed by sectioning below the shear lip, polishing to optical finish, and viewing in the SEM. Figures 7 a and b show representative crack tips for fractures in the whisker and particulate material, respectively. In both cases, the crack is observed to propagate in the matrix material by growth of voids at the ends of SiC particles. The crack path is not constantly perpendicular to the applied load direction but follows regions of high SiC reinforcement density in a wavy pattern keeping the "average crack direction" perpendicular to the load. Crack process zone voids are highly localized and were not observed more than two times the mean particle spacing from the plane of the crack except in a region of high damage near the root of the notch. These observations are in accord with those of Mukherji and Chellman (17) on fatigued SiC_w/6061-T6.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7 - SEM micrographs of crack tip process zones in SiC/6061 Al MMC: a) whisker reinforced material and b) particulate reinforced material.

Observations of compact tension specimen fracture surfaces in the SEM revealed five distinct morphological features. These features varied widely in frequency of occurrence on the fracture surface and, in decreasing frequency of observation, are:

- (1) Dimples - Most of the fracture surface consisted of fine, equiaxed dimples of uniform size. Figure 8 shows an example of this morphology. Embedded in the base of approximately 50% of these dimples is the tip of a SiC particle which according to Arsenault and Pande (18) is covered with a coating of aluminum matrix. Quantitative stereo pair measurements of the mean dimple diameter and height are shown in Table 6 along with additional microstructural data, some of which was obtained from optical micrographs.

Figure 8 - SEM fractograph showing representative dimple morphology.

TABLE 6: MICROSTRUCTURAL PARAMETERS

	MATERIAL	ORIENT	MFD(μm)	Sp(μm)	d_0 (μm)	D (μm)	h (μm)
PLATE	25 v/o SiC _p /6061 T6	L	9.7	13.0	3.3	3.9	1.37
	25 v/o SiC _p /6061 T6	T	8.7	11.5	2.8	3.7	1.24
	20 v/o SiC _w /6061 T6	L	2.2	2.8	0.6*	1.2	0.63
	20 v/o SiC _w /6061 T6	T	3.3	4.1	0.8*	1.1	0.55
TUBE	20 v/o SiC _w /6061 T6	L	3.9	4.5	0.9*	1.8	1.60
	20 v/o SiC _w /6061 T6	R	3.5	4.3	0.8*	1.6	0.88
	20 v/o SiC _w /6061 T6	C	3.4	4.5	1.1*	1.3	0.75
MFD = MEAN FREE DISTANCE		Sp = PARTICLE SPACING		d_0 = MEAN PARTICLE DIAMETER			
D = MEAN DIMPLE DIAMETER		*(CALCULATED AS Sp-MFD)		h = MEAN DIMPLE HEIGHT			

- (2) Inclusions - Both iron rich and chromium rich inclusions were observed. An example is shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 9 - Stereo pair/SEM fractograph of cracked inclusion (from J. Ahearn and C. Cooke, ref. 3).

- (3) Non-bonded regions - Regions of non-bonded matrix material were observed only on the fracture surface of the extruded tube material. Figure 10 shows an example where it appears that SiC

Figure 10 - SEM fractograph showing non-bonded region.

was pressed into the matrix material during fabrication but bonding apparently did not occur. These non-bonded regions appeared either coplanar with the plane of fracture or in the base of depressions called "fisheyes".

- (4) Regions of Non-Infiltration - Areas which lacked matrix material as shown in Fig. 11 were rather rare. In earlier whisker material these features were more numerous, but improvements in mixing and consolidation processing have greatly reduced the frequency of these defects. They were not observed in the particulate material.

Figure 11 - SEM fractograph showing non-infiltrated region.

- (5) Decohesion at Al grain boundaries - Occasional decohesion at aluminum grain boundaries was observed in the whisker material. The resulting morphology shown in Fig. 12a is distinguished from that shown in Fig. 8 by the location of the SiC at the edge of the dimples. The relative location of the boundaries and the SiC particles can be compared with the TEM micrograph of Fig. 12b. The triple point void shown in Fig. 12a is not always present with this type of morphology.

Fractographic observations of CVN specimens revealed a sixth morphological feature on some of the fracture surface area as shown in Fig. 13. This morphology was not observed on tensile or fracture toughness specimen fracture surfaces and may explain the opposite response to heat treatment seen between K_{Ic} and CVN behavior.

Microstructural Interpretation of Fracture Toughness

To understand the composite fracture behavior and its connection with the microstructure of the material, it is necessary to understand the micromechanical processes which occur in the material adjacent to a crack tip. Figure 14 shows a schematic of the processes leading to fracture as a sharp crack is loaded. The micromechanical processes are envisioned as follows: First, crack tip blunting occurs with the development of a

(a)

(b)

Figure 12 - a) SEM fractograph showing decohesion at Al grain boundaries and b) TEM micrograph showing relation of whisker to grain boundaries (from J. Ahearn and C. Cooke, ref. 3).

Figure 13 - SEM fractograph of CVN specimen.

Figure 14 - Schematic of micromechanical fracture processes leading to failure in SiC/6061 Al MMC.

small-scale plastic zone in front of the crack tip. As the crack surfaces move apart by an apparent crack tip opening displacement, δ_t , the crack length increases. The developing plastic zone interacts with the microstructure, plastic flow becomes concentrated around the embedded SiC particles, and a process zone is established in which voids are opened at the ends of SiC particles. When crack tip blunting ceases, the voids formed in front of the crack grow by the stretching of the matrix in the ligaments. As the surfaces move apart and the matrix material at the crack tip reaches tensile instability, a chisel edge is formed and the leading void coalesces with the crack tip. The real crack tip opening displacement at this stage is limited to the void height, $2h$, since the opening deformation is limited to the growth and coalescence of the next void.

It is worthwhile to discuss the processes in more detail so that the factors affecting each stage of the fracture can be delineated.

Crack-Tip Blunting. The mechanics of the crack tip blunting process for small scale yielding have been developed from continuum mechanics and from finite element analyses. When a plastic material containing a sharp crack is loaded, the stress intensity at the crack tip causes the crack to blunt. Volumetric constancy under plane strain conditions, where $\epsilon_{zz}=0$, imposes a contraction in the x-direction ($\epsilon_{xx} = -\epsilon_{yy}$). A triaxial stress state containing a hydrostatic tensile stress is developed in front of the crack and a diamond shaped region of intense plastic strain is formed as the crack surfaces move apart by an apparent crack tip opening displacement, δ_t . The contraction ϵ_{xx} increases the length of the crack.

A convenient representation of the stress field surrounding the crack is obtained by constructing a slip-line diagram showing lines of maximum shear stress. The slip-line field near a tensile crack and its modification due to crack tip blunting are shown in Fig. 15. The region of intense plastic strain is labelled D and, according to Rice and Johnston (19), extends a distance of $\sim 1.9\delta_t$ ahead of the crack where δ_t is the crack tip opening displacement. Finite element analyses of the problem for small-scale yielding have been performed by several researchers. The results obtained by McMeeking (20) for a material which work hardens indicate that the plastic strain along the plane of the crack falls to a low value within a distance of $\sim 4\delta_t$. On a plane inclined 45° to the crack, the plastic strain remains at a high value for a much greater distance (i.e. $\sim 12\delta_t$) posing the possibility that a shear decohesion process might operate.

Figure 15 - Schematic showing slip-line field at crack: a) initial configuration of sharp notch and b) configuration after blunting.

The results further indicate that, for a stationary crack, δ_t is related to the stress intensity, K_I , at the crack tip by:

$$\delta_t = \frac{\alpha K_I^2}{\sigma_y E} \quad (5)$$

where α is a non-dimensional numerical constant which depends on the material work hardening exponent, n . When $n=0.0, 0.1$ and 0.2 then $\alpha \sim 0.66, 0.4,$ and $0.2,$ respectively. For the SiC/Al materials studied, the work hardening exponents ranged between 0.063 and 0.120 producing values for α between 0.35 and 0.5

Localization of Strain at Second Phase Particles. As the plastic zone develops in front of the crack tip, it envelops second phase particles which act as stress risers. On a microscale, the local stress and strain fields in the matrix near the embedded particles are modified and become potential sites for the opening of voids. It is expected that the hydrostatic tension developed in front of the crack would aid in the formation of the process zone. The hydrostatic tension adds a tensile component to the stress normal to the SiC/Al interface and is therefore expected to aid the formation of voids at second phase particles. After void nucleation occurs, the hydrostatic tension would accelerate void growth. The local stress state is conveniently represented by the equivalent stress, $\bar{\sigma}$, and the hydrostatic component, σ_m , where

$$\bar{\sigma} = [(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)^2]^{0.5} / \sqrt{2} \quad (6)$$

and

$$\sigma_m = 1/3 (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3) \quad (7)$$

where σ_1 , σ_2 , and σ_3 are the principal stresses. The degree of triaxiality is represented by the ratio $\sigma_m/\bar{\sigma}$ which is infinite for pure hydrostatic stress ($\sigma_1=\sigma_2=\sigma_3$) and zero for pure shear ($\sigma_1=-\sigma_2$, $\sigma_3=0$) (21).

The problem of elastic inclusions embedded in work hardening and non-work hardening elastic-plastic matrices has been treated by a number of authors (22-25). The predominant feature of these analyses is that a radial stress develops across the particle/matrix interface which initially has a maximum above the pole of the inclusion. The magnitude of this maximum radial stress, σ_{rr} is approximately

$$\sigma_{rr} \sim 1.5\tau_y + \sigma_m \quad (8)$$

where τ_y is the shear yield strength of the matrix. As deformation proceeds and the strain field develops, the position of the maximum radial strain shifts away from the pole. Yielding in the matrix does not occur at the particle/matrix interface but rather at a small distance from the interface (25).

The interfacial stress is also expected to be a function of the volume fraction of reinforcing particles in the process zone since yielding between particles is expected to increase σ_{rr} above that predicted by eq. (8) when the particles are sufficiently closely spaced. Results indicate that when the volume fraction exceeds ~ 0.1 , interparticle interactions occur from the onset of plastic yielding.

Development of Fracture Process Zone. The fracture process zone develops as the stress and strain fields in front of the crack reach sufficient intensity to open voids in the material. While a few pre-existing voids from fabrication may be present in the material, (Fig. 2a), additional voids can be nucleated either by fracture of the SiC particles or by separation at or near the particle/matrix interface. The predominant fractographic observation is that the voids open at the ends of SiC particles adjacent to the crack plane. Evidence also indicates that decohesion occurs in the matrix leaving a thin coating of matrix material to cover the SiC particle (18). It is not known how the void is nucleated in the aluminum but most probably nucleation occurs at some defect or other matrix phase such as Mg₂Si precipitates in the aluminum; the significant point being that the nucleation is associated with stress/strain localization caused by the SiC particles. Fractographic examination of dimple morphology and crack profile sections indicates that fracture initiation results primarily from normal strain, ϵ_{yy} , rather than shear strains.

Void initiation at hard particles has been analyzed by a number of authors in terms of a stress criteria and/or strain criteria for decohesion at the particle matrix interface. Recent reviews by Goods and Brown (27) and by Wilsdorf (28) reveal the complexity of the problem. The interplay between the stress/strain fields and void nucleation ahead of a blunting crack in small-scale yielding has been developed by Hancock and Cowling (21). They point out that in the small-scale yielding case for a strain dominated nucleation criteria, nucleation occurs at the location where strain values are equal to the nucleation strain, independent of the stress state triaxiality. For a stress fracture dominated criteria, decohesion

depends on the interfacial stress which arises from both the hydrostatic component and a contribution from work hardening (eq. 8). Hancock and Cowling's results indicate that for the SiC/Al MMC's in the present investigation where $n \approx 0.1$, the radial stress developed across the interface at particles located in the crack tip plastic zone is approximately constant in the range $0.1 < X/\delta_t < 2$, but the plastic strain decreases rapidly in the same distance.

Void Growth and Coalescence. Void growth and coalescence has also been extensively treated in recent years. McClintock (29) describes the growth of voids by treating the expansion of elliptical prismatic cavities. The strain to fracture, ϵ_f , assuming no void interaction and fracture when growing holes touch is,

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{(1-n) \ln (\alpha/f^{1/3})}{\sinh [(1-n) (\sigma_a + \sigma_b) \sqrt{3/2\bar{\sigma}}]} \quad (9)$$

where n is the strain hardening exponent, $(\sigma_a + \sigma_b)/\bar{\sigma}$ is the ratio of transverse to equivalent stress, f is the initial volume fraction of voids, and α is a geometric constant. The major prediction is that the ductility increases with the work hardening rate and with decreasing void volume fraction. A strong dependence of fracture strain on stress triaxiality is also established.

Tracey (30) considers the growth of isolated spherical voids under conditions of high stress triaxiality and predicts the void growth rate to be

$$\frac{\Delta R}{\Delta \epsilon R_0} = c \exp \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}\sigma}{2\tau_y} \right) \quad (10)$$

where R_0 is the initial void radius, $\Delta \epsilon$ and σ are the remote strain increment and applied stress, and τ_y is the shear yield strength. The model predicts rapid void growth for highly triaxial stress states.

Rice and Johnson (19) considered spherical inclusions of radius R_0 at a distance X_0 ahead of a crack. Assuming no bonding between the matrix and the inclusion and that the growing void would coalesce when the distance between the crack tip and the void became equal to the vertical radius of the growing void, they obtained a graphical representation between δ_t/X_0 and X_0/R_0 . For a fixed volume fraction of inclusions the model predicts K_{IC} is proportional to $\sqrt{X_0}$.

For ductile fracture to initiate from a sharp crack, the crack tip opening displacement at fracture δ_i , must approach a size comparable to the process zone size, Δl . In principle, Δl should also relate to the parameter c in eq. 3. If rupture occurs as the process zone exceeds a critical distance Δl , then

$$\Delta l = k \delta_i \quad (11)$$

where k is a constant. Δl may then be related to appropriate microstructural parameters. In practice, $0.5 < k < 2.0$, with low k values being favored when voids are not easily nucleated. High values of k are favored when the volume fraction is large, when there are multiple populations of void nucleating sites, or when a shear decohesion mechanism is operable (26).

Using eq. 11 and the results from Figs. 6a and b extrapolated to $\rho=0$, the extent of the process zone is estimated as $3 \mu\text{m} < \Delta l_w < 12 \mu\text{m}$ for whisker material and $12 \mu\text{m} < \Delta l_p < 50 \mu\text{m}$ for particulate material at a sharp notch. Therefore, the process zone is expected to extend between one and three particle spacings. Observations of void nucleation at second phase particles would be highly localized to the crack tip. The SEM micrographs of the crack tip region shown in Figs. 7a and b confirm the expected confinement of the process zone.

The above theories can be used to calculate the fracture toughness, K_{IC} . Bates (31) has refined the Rice-Johnson and McMeeking models to calculate K_{IC} for a void coalescence mechanism constrained in small-scale yielding. Bates takes $\alpha = 0.6$ and then derives the following relationships between the dimple diameter, D_d , the dimple height, h , and the particle diameter, d_0 :

$$\delta_{T1} = \frac{[1.924 (\delta_{T2}/\delta_{T1}) - 0.299] d_0}{2.237 - 0.337(\delta_{T2}/\delta_{T1})} \quad (12)$$

$$\delta_{t1c} = \delta_{T2} + \frac{1}{2} [1.67(\delta_{T2}/\delta_{T1}) - 0.67] d_0 \quad (13)$$

where $(\delta_{T2}/\delta_{T1}) = \frac{D^*/d_0 + 0.048}{1.298}, \quad (14)$

and $D^* = D_d + h/2 \quad (15)$

The above equations are solved simultaneously for δ_{t1c} and then eq. (5) is used to calculate K_{IC} by letting $\delta_t \rightarrow \delta_{t1c}$ as $K_I \rightarrow K_{IC}$.

A simpler approach is to assume that the crack grows as the leading void in the process zone coalesces with the crack tip. Then $\delta_{t1c} \sim 2h$ and from eq. (5), with appropriate values for α ,

$$K_{IC} \approx \left[\frac{2E\sigma_y h}{\alpha} \right]^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

A comparison of the predictions of the calculated K_{IC} values from the Bates model and from eq. (16) with measured toughness data is shown in Table 7. Both models give good agreement.

TABLE 7: COMPARISON OF CALCULATED AND MEASURED FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

MATERIAL	ORIENT	K_{IC} CALCULATED ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$) EQ's (12)-(15)	K_{IC} CALCULATED ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$) EQ (16)	K_{IC} MEASURED ($\text{MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$)
20% SiC _w /6061-T6 PLATE	L-T	18.1	13.9	7.1
	T-L	9.9	9.0	6.3
25% SiC _p /6061-T6 PLATE	L-T	17.4	14.4	15.8
	T-L	18.2	13.9	14.5
20% SiC _w /6061-DG + T6 TUBE	L-C	16.2	16.2	22.4

While all the void growth models emphasize the need for high local strains to cause rupture, most of them overestimate the strain required and ignore void interactions. Void interactions would tend to lower the strain requirements and would therefore compensate to some degree the overestimation of the strain. Thomason (32) accounts for void interaction by assuming unstable internal necking of the ligaments between voids. The influence of the matrix/particle cohesive bond strength on the internal necking mechanism of ductile failure caused by nucleation of voids at second phase particles has also been analyzed (33) and a model relating material properties to fracture toughness has been presented (34). This model is limited to volume fractions, V_f , less than 9%, and predicts:

$$K_{IC} = Y \left\{ \rho \left[4.62 (E/Y) \frac{(e^{\epsilon_i} - 1)}{(1-\nu^2)} + 8.81 \tan \left(\frac{\pi}{2} \left(1 - \frac{V_f}{0.09} \right) \right) \right] \right\}^{1/2} \quad (17)$$

where: Y is $\sqrt{3}\tau_y$, τ_y is the shear yield stress in uniaxial tension, ϵ_i is the instability strain in uniaxial tension, ν is Poisson's ratio, ρ is the root radius of the crack tip, V_f is the volume fraction of the void producing particles, and the expression is valid for $2\% < V_f < 9\%$. The model does not require transverse void growth until the onset of internal necking, after which transverse hole growth occurs very rapidly.

Although the present results fall outside the range of validity of Thompson's model, an important implication is that incipient fracture occurs ahead of the crack for finite root radii and that the distance ahead of the crack (Δl) decreases to zero as V_f approaches 9%. In other words, there should be little or no post-instability strain in the ligaments prior to fracture nor should there be an extensive process zone in front of the crack as fracture proceeds for $V_f > 9\%$. The last three mechanisms presented in Fig. 14 would be indistinguishable for $V_f > 9\%$. Although the present results are in qualitative agreement with this model, some process zone behavior is observed even though the composite contains 20-25 v/o reinforcement (Figs. 7 a and b).

Conclusions

The conclusions derived from this work are as follows:

1. Critical crack-tip opening displacement for fracture is a linear function of the notch root radius. This implies that fracture is a strain controlled process. The strain controlled process is hypothesized to be the nucleation and growth of voids associated with SiC particles.

2. The apparent fracture toughness fits a relationship of the form

$$K_{IC}(\rho) = K_{IC} \frac{(1+\rho/2c)^{3/2}}{(1+\rho/c)}$$

3. Fracture toughness in the SiC/Al MMC's is dependent on the projected area of SiC in the plane of fracture and this leads to an orientation dependence of K_{IC} .

4. The toughness is controlled primarily by the size, shape, and distribution of SiC in the microstructure, but is weakly dependent on the yield stress of the material.

5. The fracture behavior of SiC/Al MMC's is adequately described by continuum mechanics treatments of small-scale yielding and the behavior is consistent with a void coalescence fracture mechanism.

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